

Isolation and Identification of *Citrobacter* Species and their Antibiotic Susceptibility with Special Reference to Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamase

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Abstract:

Background: *Citrobacter* species are frequent nosocomial pathogens, a local or systemic breach in the host defences can allow them to cause a range of infections which include urinary tract infections, neonatal sepsis, pulmonary infections, meningitis and blood stream infections. *Citrobacter* species are emerging as important nosocomial pathogens. *Citrobacter* infections are associated with high mortality rate.

Objectives: To determine their antibiotic susceptibility pattern. To detect extended spectrum beta lactamase producing species.

Material and Methods: Various clinical samples received in the central lab of DMCH Darbhanga. Identification will be done by using standard microbiological techniques. Antibiotic susceptibility test will be performed by Kirby-Bauer Disc diffusion method. Test strains will be pre-incubated in peptone water at 37°C at an optical density of 0.5 McFarland standard. This suspension will be used to inoculate strains onto Muller Hinton agar plate by swabbing them with a sterile cotton swab and performing culture as recommended by clinical and laboratory standards institute. The antibiotic discs used for sensitivity testing will be obtained from Hi-Media, India, which will be used to study the sensitivity pattern.

Conclusion: The magnitude of *Citrobacter* infections has increased over time considering its potential to cause nosocomial infections and the growing numbers of immunocompromised patients in hospitals. *C.koseri* and *C.freundii* being the commonest species isolated. They are usually isolated from patients with wound infections, urinary tract infections, respiratory infections and bacteremia. The emergence of drug resistance among the *Citrobacter* is noteworthy.

Keywords: *Citrobacter spp*, *Citrobacter* infections, UTI, Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern, ESBL.

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Introduction

These bacilli are commonly distributed in soil, sewage, water & food. The importance of this species lies in their association with serious nosocomial infections and high degree resistance to common antimicrobial agents used for the treatment of various infections [1]. *Citrobacter species* and *Serratia marcescens* constituted 1-2% of nosocomial bloodstream, cardiovascular and ear, nose and throat infections [1]. Although *Citrobacter species* are infrequent nosocomial pathogens, local or systemic breaches of host defenses can allow them to cause a range of infections. These include urinary tract infections, neonatal sepsis, brain abscess, meningitis, bloodstream infections, intra-abdominal sepsis, and pneumonia [2]. The *Citrobacter species* are emerging as important nosocomial pathogens. Antibiotic resistance is emerging in the isolates of *Enterobacteriaceae* and in other gram negative bacilli in many parts of the world and this is a major threat to the successful treatment

of infections in hospitals [3]. The *Citrobacter* infections are associated with a high mortality rate. They are often resistant to the routinely used antibiotics, especially the extended spectrum cephalosporins, due to the overexpression of chromosomal beta lactamases [3]. Urinary tract infection (UTI) continues to be the commonest nosocomial infection according to approximately 40% of all hospital acquired infections and it is one of the most important causes of morbidity and mortality [4]. Urinary tract infection (UTI) is the third most common infection experienced by humans after respiratory and gastro-intestinal infections [4]. *Citrobacter* isolates were found to be the third most common organism causing UTI in hospitalized patients after *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* species accounting to 9.4% of all isolates. It is a present challenge to the clinical microbiologist because of their increased occurrence in nosocomial infection [4]. extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) have become

more and more prevalent in species characterized by inducible class C cephalosporinase (AmpC) such as *Citrobacter freundii* and *Serratia marcescens*, which frequently segregate mutants with high-level constitutive production of AmpC enzymes [5]. Although the resistance rates of *Serratia sp* and *Citrobacter sp* to third-generation cephalosporins are considerably high in India, studies on the resistance mechanisms to extended-spectrum cephalosporins among these species have been rarely performed here [5]. Increasing drug resistance due to empirical treatment in UTI needs regular monitoring of the antibiotic susceptibility of uropathogens in a particular area. Various factors such as the type of UTI (complicated or uncomplicated), gender, age, and previous history of antibiotic therapy or instrumentation of each UTI patient should also be considered to find out the correct global data on susceptibility [6]. Isolated pathogen frequency and antimicrobial resistant rates can vary dramatically even within the same country. To ensure appropriate therapy current knowledge of the pathogens that cause UTI in an area and their susceptibility pattern is mandatory [7].

Objectives: To isolate and identify *Citrobacter species* from various clinical samples, study the antibiotic susceptibility of *Citrobacter species* isolated, detect the occurrence of extended spectrum beta-lactamase producers in the *Citrobacter species* isolated.

Material and Methods

Total of 100 clinical samples from the Various clinical samples received in the central lab of Darbhanga medical college and Hospital Laheriasarai, Bihar. Study duration of two years. Identification will be done by using standard microbiological techniques. Antibiotic susceptibility test will be

performed by Kirby-Bauer Disc diffusion method. Test strains will be pre-incubated in peptone water at 37°C at an optical density of 0.5McFarland standard. This suspension will be used to inoculate strains onto Muller Hinton agar plate by swabbing them with a sterile cotton swab and performing culture as recommended by clinical and laboratory standards institute. The antibiotic discs used for sensitivity testing will be obtained from Hi-Media, India, which will be used to study the sensitivity pattern.

Test strains were pre-incubated in peptone water at 37°C at an optical density of 0.5McFarland standard. This suspension was used to inoculate strains onto Muller Hinton agar plate by swabbing them with a sterile cotton swab. In this test 30microgram antibiotic disc of ceftazidime, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone and aztreonam are placed on the plate, 30mm from the amoxicillin/clavulanate (20/10 microgram) disc. A clear extension of the edge of the cephalosporin inhibition zone towards the disk containing clavulanate is interpreted as synergy, indication ESBL production. The British society of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy has recommended the disk diffusion method for phenotypic confirmation of ESBL presence using ceftazidime/ clavulanate and cefotaxime/ clavulanate combination disc with semiconfluent growth on Iso-sensitiser agar. The zone diameter of each combination is compared with zone diameter of cephalosporin along a ratio of cephalosporin/clavulanate zone diameter to cephalosporinzone size is clavulanate. A ratio of >1.5 or greater indicates the presence of ESBL.

No of *Citrobacter* isolates in different age groups

Age Group (Years)	No of Isolates (Percentage)
0-10	7 (7%)
11-20	4 (4%)
21-30	16 (16%)
31-40	26 (26%)
41-50	17 (17%)
51-60	9 (9%)
61-70	13 (13%)
71-80	5 (5%)
81-90	3 (3%)
TOTAL	100

no of *Citrobacter spp* isolated in different age groups. Maximum isolates were in the age group of 31-40y (26) and least isolates were in the age group of 81-90y.

No of *Citrobacter spp* in different sex

Sex	No of Isolates (Percentage)
Males	56 (56%)
Females	44 (44%)
Total	100

no of *Citrobacter spp* isolated in males (56)and females(44).

Speciation of Citrobacter

Organism isolated	No of isolates (percentage)
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	18 (18%)
<i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	82 (82%)

percentage of ESBL producers in *Citrobacter spp*

Organism	Percentage
ESBL Producers	62%
NON-ESBL Producers	38%

information regarding no. Of ESBL producers in *Citrobacter spp*

Discussion

All the samples which have come for the culture and sensitivity testing are taken as test samples in this study the samples such as urine, pus, sputum, wound discharge, etc were collected and processing was done accordingly. The observation of this study is as follows.[8]

During this study period, all the 100 *Citrobacter spp* isolates from all the age groups are taken. In this study, maximum *Citrobacter spp* isolates were from 31y-40y i.e., 26% followed by 41y-50y(17%), 21y-30y(16%), 61y-70y(13%), 51y-60y(9%), 0-10y(7%), 71y-80y(5%), 11y-20y(4%) and least number of *Citrobacter spp* are isolated from 81y- 90y of age group showing about 3% of total isolates whereas in study conducted by Ritu Nayar, Indu Shukla, Asfia Sultan, maximum number of isolates were from 11- 20y of age i.e., 21.9% and least number of *Citrobacter spp* were isolated from age >60y about 0.95%[1]. Similar results are observed in another study done by Hiba Sami, Asfia Sultana, Meher Rizvi et al, which states most of the *Citrobacter spp.* were isolated in the 20–30(43.4%) and 30–40 year(17.7%) age group [13]. In contrary, a study done by Basavaraj C Metri, P. Jyothi, Basavaraj V Peerapur, shows 35.5% of isolates are from age>61y followed by 41-60y(25%) and least in 21-40y(17.1%) [9] In the study done by Shobha K.L, Akshatha S.J, Amin Sonam G.S, Out of 160 patients 34 were females (52.3%) and 31 were males (47.69%) [4]. In another study done by Hiba Sami, Asfia Sultana, Meher Rizvi et al, among the 246 (3.46%) patients positive for *Citrobacter spp.*, 193 were females (78.4%) and 53 males (21.5%) [13]. But in our study out of 100 patients whose samples isolated *Citrobacter spp.*, there are 56% of males and 44% of female patients. There is increase *Citrobacter* isolates in males more than females. In our study, most of the *Citrobacter spp* are isolated from urine sample which accounts to 61%, followed by pus sample which were isolated 18%, then sputum - 14%, other samples like vaginal swab-4%, nasal discharge-1%, blood-1% and fluid-1%. In a study done by Basavaraj C Metri et al 55% of patients *Citrobacter spp* are isolated due to indwelling

urethral catheterisation or genitourinary instrumentation or due to obstructive uropathy. The possible reasons for high frequency in elderly male include obstructive uropathy due to prostate enlargement, loss of bactericidal activity of prostatic secretions frequent genitourinary instrumentation and catheterisation. *Citrobacter koseri* was the predominant organism accounting 72.4% of isolates [14]. In a study done by Glenn R. Hodges. M.D. et al 37 of 83(45%) suspected infections are due to *Citrobacter* involved the urinary tract. All the patients were male ranging in age from 23 to 86years. 18 of 37 (49%) episodes in this group were significant infections. 16 of 37(43%) infections were intermediate, and in 3 cases (8%) the isolates were commensals [15]. In another study done by Hiba Sami, Asfia Sultan et al. The prevalence of *Citrobacter sppis* 3.46% when compared to other studies which showed 9.4%. Almost half of the patients were belonged to 21-30 years of age group affected by UTI caused by *Citrobacter spp.* According to our study, the best sensitive drug for treating *Citrobacter* infections is gentamicin (89.7%), Amikacin (83%), Nitrofurantoin (86.8%) followed by ofloxacin (51.2%), Cefotaxime (45%), Cefazidime(37%), Ceftriaxone(35%), Ciprofloxacin (33%), Norfloxacin(24.5%) and Nalidixic acid(19.6%). A study done by Basavaraj C Metri et al, says majority of the UTI s were found to be resistant to Cefotaxime, Cephalaxin, norfloxacin, Ciprofloxacin and the aminoglycosides but since good invitro activity was shown by nitrofurantoin it may be considered as first line oral therapy in ambulatory patients [12]. In a study done by Liun Liu, Daoli Chen et al, most of the 82 *C. freundii* isolates were resistant to beta-lactams, especially to penicillins(41.5%), Cephalosporins (19.5%-98.8) and monobactams (25.6%) resistance to two quinolones (ciprofloxacin and levofloxacin) tested was 7.3 and 2.4% respectively.; resistance to other antibiotics included aminoglycosides (2.4-11.0%), phenicols(2.4%), sulphonamides (6.1%), tetracyclines (8.5%) and nitrofurantoin (13.4%) [16]. But in a study done by Glenn R. Hodges et al, the drug pattern was little different. Here, more than 90% isolates of *C.freundii* from 21infectious episodes and *C. 5* isolates showed resistant to all the first line of drugs which were further processed to check sensitivity pattern for second line of drugs. The

following is the sensitivity pattern of second line of drugs used in the present study: Imipenem (60%), Meropenem (80%), Azithromycin (40%), levofloxacin (60%), Linezolid(0%), Clindamycin(0%) and Piperacillin tazobactam(0%). But in a study done by C Rodrigues et al, ESBL producers in *Citrobacter spp* is accounted to 33.33% where one out of three isolates produced beta-lactamase enzyme [17]. In another study done Neena V. Nagdeo, Navinchanda M. Kaore, Vilas R. Thombare, 15 *Citrobacter spp* were isolated and were processed for ESBL detection. Following which 8 isolates were ESBL producers accounting for 53.33% in *Citrobacter* alone [18]. There is about 50% incidence of ESBL production among *Citrobacter spp* isolated. *Citrobacter* and similar species may play a unique role in bacterial evolution. They are of low virulence and thus can persist in a host population for long periods. Over time, they could accumulate resistance determinants which may then be available for transfer to more virulent organisms [19].

Conclusion

The magnitude of *Citrobacter* infections has increased over time considering its potential to cause nosocomial infections and the growing numbers of immunocompromised patients in hospitals. *C.koseri* and *C.freundii* being the commonest species isolated. They are usually isolated from patients with wound infections, urinary tract infections, respiratory infections and bacteremia. These are monomicrobial in 83% of cases but polymicrobial infection can also be encountered. *Citrobacter* infection can cause infection in any age group with significant predilection in adolescent and middle age. Infection is seen in both sexes with significant proportion in males.

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